

Study of Adding Different Levels of Aqueous Extract of Cloves to Water and Its Effect on the Productive Traits of Broilers

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Abstract:

This experiment was conducted in the poultry field belonging to the Agricultural Research and Experimentation Station at the College of Agriculture / Karbala for the period from 10/6/2022 until 11/9/2023. The current study aimed to demonstrate the effect of using different levels of aqueous extract of clove powder added to drinking water and its effect on some productive traits of broiler chickens. A cage with dimensions of 1.5 x 1 m, with 30 chicks for each treatment, with three replicates of the treatment (10 chicks for each replicate), and with four treatments, namely T1, the control treatment without any addition. As for treatments T2, T3, and T4, aqueous extract of clove powder was added to it in three concentrations (10, 20, and 30). ml/liter of drinking water, respectively. The results of the experiment indicated a significant improvement ($p \leq 0.05$) in the productive characteristics of the clove powder aqueous extract treatments. Treatment T4 (30 ml/liter of drinking water) witnessed a significant improvement ($p \leq 0.05$) in body weight and weight gain and an increase in the food conversion factor with a decrease Significant ($p \leq 0.05$) in the percentage of deaths, compared to the control treatment.

Keywords: *aqueous extract, cloves, medical plants, productive traits, broilers.*

Introduction

Modern breeds of broilers are characterized by rapid growth and high weight rates, in addition to a high feed conversion factor (N.C.C., 2016). As a result, the immunity of birds has decreased significantly, as it was found that there is a

negative correlation coefficient between the immune response of birds and the speed of growth of broilers (Qureshi, & Havenstein, 1994). This has prompted many breeders to Excessive use of antibiotics causes health damage in addition to making some bacterial strains resistant to these antibiotics (Muir,

Bryden, & Husband, 2000), which negatively affects the health of birds and the health of the consumer, as well as a decrease in the performance of broilers (Al-Zubaidi, 2016). Therefore, researchers paid attention to medicinal herbs and their use because of their benefits. It has an important role in treating several diseases, as well as the absence of negative effects on the health of birds and the consumer. Among these medicinal plants are Gujarat (Al-Gharawi, 2018), olive leaves (Al-Aboudi, 2016). Among these medicinal plants is cloves, which are a group of unopened pink buds that are brown in color with a smell. Pungent, cloves are considered one of the important plants that are used as a food preservative and as a very rich source of antioxidant compounds. It has been used in the development of many medicinal products that have been used in the production of medicinal drugs (Cortés-Rojas, de Souza, & Oliveira, 2014). It has many benefits due to the active substances it possesses in addition to the fact that it contains Phenolic compounds that have an antibacterial and antibacterial effect and are used as a local antiseptic. Likewise, clove oils obtained through the distillation process help improve the digestive process and are used as an antibacterial (Al-Jebory, & Al-Jaryan, 2023). Cloves also contain volatile oils and tannins, in addition to containing a group of active compounds, carbohydrates and vitamins. c, b (Merrill, & Perry, 2009). Clove oil and its aqueous extracts are also considered to have antiseptic, anti-inflammatory and antioxidant activity. In addition, cloves are considered an appetite stimulant and improve digestion (Cortés-Rojas, de Souza, & Oliveira, 2014; Al-Jebory, & Al-Jaryan, 2023). Therefore, the current study aimed to study the effect of different levels of aqueous clove extract on the productive traits of broilers.

Materials and Methods

Preparation of the Aqueous Extract and Method of Use

Cloves were obtained from Karbala Governorate and ground using a small electric grinder to form a powder ready for use. The extract was then prepared according to the modified method (Khalil Ibrahim, & Hadi Dakhil Al-jebory, 2020) by mixing an amount of dry powder with an amount of distilled water in a ratio of 1 gm: 2 ml distilled water using a blender. Electrophoresis and exposed the solution to a temperature of 60 degrees Celsius for one hour and left the solution for 24 hours at room temperature, after which the solution was filtered through a number of layers of sterile medical gauze to be ready for use in the experiment.

Chicken Management

The hatched chicks were raised in four-storey batteries with an area of 1.5 m x 1 m. Each floor contained 10 broiler chicks (each floor represented one replicate for each treatment). The temperature was regulated using a mercury thermometer from the age of one day until the marketing age (35). (days), using gas incubators and air extractors, while providing all special conditions for raising broiler chickens, while providing free feed and water, and using a continuous lighting system 23 hours a day during the first three days of the chicks' life, while giving one hour of darkness for the purpose of accustoming the chicks and preventing their disturbance and crowding, and the number of hours was reduced. Lighting gradually to be 8 hours a day at the age of 21 days until marketing. The extract was also added to the drinking water from the aqueous extract from the age of one day until the end of the experiment.

I used plastic feed dishes with a diameter of 38 cm in the first week, one dish for each floor, then they were gradually replaced with the longitudinal metal feeders used in the battery rearing system, 1.5 meters long, 10 cm wide and 15 cm deep. Clean water was prepared and presented in inverted plastic manholes with a capacity of 5 liters during the two weeks. The first two years of age. They were then replaced with longitudinal metal manholes until the end

of the experiment, and they were constantly raised to the level of the birds' chest as they aged to facilitate drinking water freely. The birds were fed two types of diets, the starter diet from the age of 1-21 days (21.92% protein and 2990 kcal/kg of representative energy feed) and Al-Nahi forage from the age of 22 days until the end of the experiment at the age of 35 days (19.70% protein and 3100 kcal/kg of representative energy feed) and the feed provided to the birds in the form of tablets (produced by the Iraqi Ghadeer Babel Company, private sector).

Studied Traits

The productive traits studied: body weight, weight gain, feed consumed, feed conversion ratio, mortality rate and production index according to Khalil Ibrahim, & Hadi Dakhil Al-jebory (2020). Statistical analysis by using the SAS, and the Duncan test used (SAS, 2012; Duncan, 1955).

Results and Discussion

Live Body Weight and Weight Gain

Table 1 and 2: shown the effect of study in live body weight. The weight gain change, in the first week noted not significant effect. In second, third, fourth and, fifth weeks and total weight gain significant increase ($P \leq 0.05$) for T2, T3 and, T4 treatments compared to T1 treatment.

The increase in the average body weight and the weight gain in the coefficients of the aqueous extract of clove powder may be attributed to the active substances present in the clove powder that work to increase appetite, which increases feed consumption and thus improves body weight (Al-Jebory, & Naji, 2021), or it may be due to its anti-pathogenic property. Which improves digestive properties (Hamady, et al., 2016). This result was consistent with what was observed by Al-Jebory, & Khaleel, (2021), who indicated that improving the general health of broilers through the use of plant extracts improves body weight and weight gain. There is a positive correlation between the general health of broilers and body weight, as the metabolic processes in the digestive system will be activated, which facilitates the processes of digestion and absorption, and thus its positive results are reflected in broilers (Rajani, Torshizi, & Rahimi, 2011). Thus, clove powder extract is considered a natural antibiotic, as it has effectiveness against pathogenic bacteria and harmful microorganisms, and thus reduces the number of harmful microorganisms compared to beneficial microorganisms and bacteria that improve the efficiency of digestion and facilitate the absorption process, as tannins stimulate some enzymes secreted by the stomach to facilitate the digestion process (Abdel Rahman, et al., 2013).

Table 1. The Effect of Using Aqueous Extract of Clove Powder on the Average Weekly Body Weight (g) of Broilers $\pm$ Standard Error

Treatments/ weeks	1	2	3	4	5
T₁	110.85 $\pm$ 0.86	297.21 $\pm$ 1.74 b	596.03 $\pm$ 4.42 bc	1148.42 $\pm$ 8.81 c	1831.59 $\pm$ 13.03 c
T₂	111.08 $\pm$ 0.77	302.54 $\pm$ 2.08 a	616.11 $\pm$ 5.06 a	1202.19 $\pm$ 8.50 b	1934.01 $\pm$ 12.72 b
T₃	111.15 $\pm$ 0.80	303.78 $\pm$ 1.96 a	620.02 $\pm$ 5.13 a	1210.28 $\pm$ 9.01 ab	1952.52 $\pm$ 12.66 ab
T₄	111.21 $\pm$ 0.66	304.33 $\pm$ 1.84 a	622.76 $\pm$ 4.82 a	1219.46 $\pm$ 9.67 a	1970.02 $\pm$ 13.15 a
Significant	N.S	*	*	*	*

Note: T1: control treatment. T2, T3, T4: Adding the aqueous extract of clove powder at levels of 10, 20, and 30 ml/liter. N.S. no significant differences * Different letters within one column indicate with significant differences between at 0.05.

Table 2. The Effect of Using Aqueous Extract of Clove Powder on Weekly Weight Gain (g) of Broilers ± Standard Error

Treatments/ weeks	1	2	3	4	5	Total
T₁	70.85± 0.59	186.36± 0.92 b	298.82± 1.63 c	552.39± 3.76 c	683.17± 4.35 d	1791.59± 12.67 d
T₂	71.08± 0.62	191.46± 1.04 a	313.57± 1.74 b	586.08± 3.55 b	731.82± 4.20 c	1894.01± 13.22 c
T₃	71.15± 0.75	192.63± 1.11 a	316.24± 2.01 ab	590.26± 3.88 ab	742.24± 5.03 b	1912.52± 12.39 b
T₄	71.21± 0.69	193.12± 0.97 a	318.43± 1.72 a	596.70± 3.63 a	750.56± 4.79 a	1930.02± 12.52 a
Significant	N.S	*	*	*	*	*

Note: T₁: control treatment. T₂, T₃, T₄: Adding the aqueous extract of clove powder at levels of 10, 20, and 30 ml/liter. N.S. no significant differences * Different letters within one column indicate with significant differences between at 0.05.

Feed Consumption

The impact of study in feed consumption shown in table (3), in first week noted no significant difference between treatments. In second, third, fourth and, fifth weeks and total feed consumption significant increase ($P \leq 0.05$) for T₂, T₃ and, T₄ treatments compared to T₁ treatment. The significant improvement in the coefficients of the aqueous extract of clove powder in feed consumption is due to active

compounds such as alkaloids, which work to increase the appetite of birds, which increases feed consumption (Al-Jebory, & Naji, 2021). Clove powder is rich in pectic compounds, which have an effective role in increasing appetite, which increases food intake. Or it may be due to the ability of clove powder to increase the effectiveness of digestive enzymes in the digestive system of birds, which prompts birds to increase feed consumption (Hamady, et al., 2016).

Table 3. The Effect of Using Aqueous Extract of Clove Powder on Feed Consumption (g) of Broilers ± Standard Error

Treatments/ weeks	1	2	3	4	5	Total
T₁	116.46± 0.88	311.69± 1.90 b	513.97± 3.66 b	983.25± 7.66 b	1304.85± 10.55 c	3230.22± 26.32 d
T₂	117.03± 0.72	313.54± 2.02 a	526.79± 4.92 a	1013.92± 8.04 a	1346.55± 10.20 b	3317.83± 27.01 c
T₃	117.12± 0.80	313.66± 1.83 a	528.12± 3.79 a	1015.25± 7.92 a	1350.27± 11.04 ab	3324.42± 26.84 b
T₄	117.16± 0.77	313.82± 1.88 a	528.59± 3.92 a	1017.17± 7.81 a	1354.73± 10.36 a	3331.47± 26.77 a
Significant	N.S	*	*	*	*	*

Note: T₁: control treatment. T₂, T₃, T₄: Adding the aqueous extract of clove powder at levels of 10, 20, and 30 ml/liter. N.S. no significant differences * Different letters within one column indicate with significant differences at 0.05

Feed Conversion Ratio

Table 4 shown the treatments effect in feed conversion ratio, we noted in the first week no significant difference among treatments. While

in second week significant improvement ($P \leq 0.05$) for T₄ compared to T₁ treatment, as well in 3rd week significant improvement ($P \leq 0.05$) for T₁, T₂ and, T₃ treatments compared to T₄, in the 4th, 5th weeks and, total

feed conversion ratio significant improvement ($P \leq 0.05$) for T2, T3 and, T4 treatments compared T1 treatment. The improvement in the food conversion factor in the aqueous extract of clove powder may be attributed to its property of inhibiting the growth of pathological microorganisms in the digestive tract, as well as its support for beneficial microorganisms, which stimulates the improvement of the secretion of digestive enzymes and thus improves the efficiency of digestion to benefit from the feed consumed, which improves the factor. Food

conversion (Moghaddam, et al., 2013). Plant extracts have an anti- and inhibitory effect on the growth of pathogenic microorganisms, thus increasing the numbers of beneficial microorganisms and then increasing the secretion of digestive enzymes, which gives better digestive efficiency to the food consumed, and this has a positive impact on the food conversion factor (Saleh, et al., 2016). Increased secretion of digestive enzymes Which improves the digestion process and thus improves the food conversion ratio.

Table 4. The Effect of Using Aqueous Extract of Clove Powder on Feed Conversion Ratio (g/b/f) of Broilers $\pm$ Standard Error

Treatments/ weeks	1	2	3	4	5	Total
T₁	1.64 $\pm$ 0.02	1.67 $\pm$ 0.02 a	1.66 $\pm$ 0.02 b	1.78 $\pm$ 0.02 a	1.91 $\pm$ 0.02 a	1.80 $\pm$ 0.02 a
T₂	1.65 $\pm$ 0.02	1.64 $\pm$ 0.01 ab	1.68 $\pm$ 0.01 b	1.73 $\pm$ 0.01 b	1.84 $\pm$ 0.01 b	1.75 $\pm$ 0.01 b
T₃	1.65 $\pm$ 0.01	1.64 $\pm$ 0.02 ab	1.67 $\pm$ 0.02 b	1.72 $\pm$ 0.01 bc	1.82 $\pm$ 0.02 bc	1.74 $\pm$ 0.01 b
T₄	1.63 $\pm$ 0.02	1.63 $\pm$ 0.01 b	1.72 $\pm$ 0.01 a	1.70 $\pm$ 0.01 c	1.80 $\pm$ 0.01 c	1.73 $\pm$ 0.01 b
Significant	N.S	*	*	*	*	*

Note: T1: control treatment. T2, T3, T4: Adding the aqueous extract of clove powder at levels of 10, 20, and 30 ml/liter. N.S. no significant differences * Different letters within one column indicate with significant differences between at 0.05.

Total Mortality and Productive Index

Mortality ratio (table 5) was increase significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) in T1 treatment compared to others, at same time T1 was had the lowest significantly ($P \leq 0.05$) in productive index compared the rest treatments. The reason for the low percentage of fatalities in the treatments of the aqueous extract of clove powder may be due to it containing tannins, which have an effective role in preventing infection by destroying the cell membrane of pathogenic bacteria, as well as blocking the effective sites of some enzymes inside the living cells of bacteria that are necessary for their growth and activity, as well as The precipitation of proteins present in the cell membrane or inside the cell causes them to permeate across the membrane, and the formation of hydrogen bonds between the free hydroxyl groups, which reflects positively on the

vitality and health of birds, and a decrease in the mortality rate. This result agreed with the findings of Al-Jebory, & Abdul-Lateef, (2024), who noted that the extract Clove powder plays an important role in reducing the percentage of deaths, and this improvement in the characteristics of production performance will be reflected positively on the values of the production index, which is considered one of the important indicators in evaluating the productive performance of broilers, which showed that high levels of ionization work to kill pathogenic bacteria from Through a change in the nature of the protein of the bacterial cell, which causes its killing, while Baqer, Gatea, & Al-Jebory, (2023) indicated that clove powder contains flavonoids and phenols that act as antibacterial agents against pathogenic microorganisms as a result of the synergistic action of these compounds that

lead to the inhibitory action of pathogenic bacteria.

Table 5. The Effect of Using Aqueous Extract of Clove Powder on Feed Conversion Ratio (g/b/f) of Broilers ± Standard Error

Treatments	Mortality ratio %	Productive index
T ₁	8.88±0.17 a	264.91±0.82 c
T ₂	4.44±0.09 b	301.42±1.01 b
T ₃	4.44±0.11 b	306.06±0.75 b
T ₄	2.22±0.13 c	318.13±0.62 a
Significant	*	*

Note: T1: control treatment. T2, T3, T4: Adding the aqueous extract of clove powder at levels of 10, 20, and 30 ml/liter. * Different letters within one column indicate with significant differences between at 0.05.

Conclusions

A significant improvement was obtained for the parameters of the aqueous extract of clove powder, which was in favor of adding the aqueous extract of clove powder at a level of 30 ml/liter in drinking water in productive characteristics such as body weight, weight gain, feed consumption, feed conversion factor, and the production evidence as a result of using the aqueous extract of clove powder to drinking water for broilers. the meat. It is possible to add clove extract to the drinking water of broilers throughout the rearing period at a level of 30 ml/liter of drinking water to obtain good production performance. Conducting further research on the use of clove aqueous extract in the drinking water of commercial laying hens, breed stock flocks, and quail, and demonstrating its effect on productive traits, and immune, physiological, and microbial traits.

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